

SOME ENGLISH PROVERBS AND THEIR EQUIVALENTS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

Kurbonova Zarina Odiljonovna

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7322610>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 5th November 2022

Accepted: 10th November 2022

Online: 15th November 2022

KEY WORDS

*Proverb, meaning, context,
equivalent, paradigm*

ABSTRACT

This article deals with proverbs and their roles in languages and the importance of them. Moreover, it indicates the similar and different peculiarities of proverbs in both Uzbek and English languages. In this article, the proverbs are analyzed, their meanings and usage contexts are studied. The most popular proverbs with similar meanings in two languages, their semantic essence is revealed.

A proverb is a brief statement that offers guidance or teaches you something about life. Both both Uzbek and English, proverbs are obviously important. Proverbs are a type of folklore that are brief and to the point, symbolic, grammatically correct, and full of significant meaning. Phrasal verbs, proverbs, sayings, and idioms are "pearls" that embellish speech, enhancing its vibrancy and expressiveness.

Proverbs and sayings are an ancient genre of folk art. They originated in a distant time, and have their roots deep into the centuries. Many of them appeared even when there was no writing. To become a proverb, a statement must be perceived and assimilated by ordinary people. Any proverb was created by a certain person in certain circumstances. Such proverbs are passed down from generation to generation. For example: "Make hay while the sun shines" ("mow hay while the sun shines"), this phrase originates from the practice of field work. But after many hundreds of people expressed this idea in

many different ways, it finally acquired its memorable form and began its life as a proverb. Similarly, the saying "Don't put all your eggs in one basket" literally means "Don't put all your eggs in one basket, arose as a result of practical experience of trade relations.

The most active category of oral art is proverbs. A proverb is a witty phrase that encapsulates the socio-historical, every day, and life experiences of a people through creative, metaphorical elements. The proverb is known as maqol in Uzbek, zarbulmasal in Tajik, paslotista in Russian, a naql in Arabic (in live speech), and ata in Turkish. The Arabic verb qawlun, which meaning to talk, is the root of the English word proverb. Paremiology is the study of proverbs and parables, according to folklore specialists. Greek word "paremiya" means "a profound word," " proverb," "a phrase," or "a saying."

G. L. Permyakov is regarded as one of the pioneers of scientific paremiology. He defined proverbs as metaphorical

statements that express a "whole thought"[1]. As a linguist and folklorist, V. Telia highlights the importance of paremiology in the relationship between culture and language. The science of paremiology, he claimed, may without a doubt reflect the culture of the speakers of a language in a beautiful and profound way, despite the fact that language represents an entire civilization. This is because linguoculture is a synthesis of various languages and cultures.

The proverbs are appreciated by author M. Gorky, who said: "The profound wisdom lies in the simplicity of the word. Songs and proverbs are constantly condensed. They possess ideas and intuitions on par with those found in entire books.

The works of William Shakespeare also express the aforementioned ideas in their proverbs and fabrics. Because even though different languages are spoken around the world, the rules of thought are universal, it is feasible to translate from one language to another. Shakespeare's time is also reflected in the proverbs and sayings of the period, which illustrate how public opinion governed life at the time.

Because they do not instantly come to mind, it is challenging to find substitutes or similar counterparts when translating proverbs, sayings, and phrases between languages.

According to G. L. Permiakov, the generalization property of instances is that when similar or identical situations are combined, a new outcome results. The proverbs' consistency assures their universality and oftentimes gives them a special logical meaning. It follows that the idea that the world of proverbs is comparable to world civilization, which is exclusive to one country, is wholly false.

Paremiology's central concept of universality in proverbs generalizes parallels and similarities in proverbs, even in different languages, independent of their historical or racial origins [2].

The nation's historical thought, which he refers to as the "autobiographical" memory of a particular group, is the source of K. Tumanishvili's proverbs. Proverbs are an example of a national form that is founded on the national system of thought and is in harmony with the nation. This is based on genetic data and naturally reflects the periphery of the ethnic group [3].

In the form of many proverbs in different languages similarities can be found in both form and meaning, or in the functions they perform in general. Some proverbs in Uzbek are functionally similar to English proverbs. For example, Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla status in Uzbek is an alternative variant Think first - then say corresponds to the proverb, because this proverb has the same meaning in both languages and its grammatical system very close. For example, In English: Give a dog a bad name and hang him. Uzbek equivalent: Yomon atalib tirik yurguncha, Yaxshi atalib o'lgan yaxshi.

He that lies down with dogs must rise up with fleas. Uzbek equivalent: Yaxshiga yondashsang, yetarsan murodga, Yomonga yondashsang, qolarsan uyatga.

In English: A good dog deserves a good bone. Uzbek equivalent: Yaxshiga ipak ilashur, yomonga tikan ilashur.

However, in translations from one language to another it will be difficult to find exactly the same proverbs. The comments are then referred to, or a second adequate option. It is very difficult to find an English version of an Uzbek proverb or an Uzbek version of an English proverb,

and commenting on the proverbs when appropriate does not impair the translation, but complements and enriches it.

Difficulties in translating English proverbs arise and have always arisen. English has its own word order, and Russian has a different one. There can never be two negatives in an English phrase, and in Russian we have just used two of them: "never", "not". An English phrase would literally sound like this: "There can never be two negatives in an English phrase."

Proverbs and sayings are a fertile material used in teaching. It covers most of the human experience. With their help, you can express your thought and summarize it in a short form. On the other hand, their study is an additional source of regional

knowledge. Proverbs and sayings can be used to process the sound side of speech. They help to put the pronunciation of certain difficult sounds, especially those that are absent in the Russian language. It is necessary to select the expression depending on which sound is being worked out.

In conclusion, Proverbs and sayings are stable expressions characteristic of any people or country, reflecting their cultural and historical heritage. We can say that this is a reflection of popular thought, attitudes and moral values. They may have analogues in other languages, so-called "equivalents" - similar in meaning, since they reproduce "simple truths" common to all people. Although they sound different.

References:

1. Mahmudov N. Tilning mukammal tadqiqi yo'llarini izlab... // O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. - Toshkent, 2012.
2. Пермяков Г.Л. Основы структурной паремиология. - Москва, 1988
3. Tumanishvili K. The specific and the Universal in the Proverb Genre / Rustaveli Institute of Georgian Literature. Volume1, 2007.
4. <http://www.wikipedia.com>
5. <http://www.google.com>
6. <http://www.thesaurus.com>